

CODEN [USA] : IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON HYPOMAGNESEMIA IN
PATIENTS OF TYPE-II DIABETES MELLITUS**¹Dr. Adil Abdul Haye, ²Dr. Abdul Nafay¹Central Park Medical College, Lahore²Medical Officer, Qilla Abdullah, Balochistan**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:****Objective:** To assess the frequency of hypomagnesemia in patients of type-II diabetes mellitus.**Material and methods:**

This cross sectional study was conducted at Department of Medicine, Central Park Medical College Lahore from August 2019 to February 2020. Total 350 type-II diabetics, having age range 30-60 years, either male or female with duration of diabetes ≥ 3 years were selected. Hypomagnesemia was assessed in selected.

Results: Total 350 type-II diabetics were selected and hypomagnesemia was assessed. Mean age of the patients 45.34 ± 8.55 years with age range from 30-60 years and mean duration of diabetes was 6.54 ± 2.43 years. Out of 350 type-II diabetics, hypomagnesemia was found in 122 (35%) patients. Total 169 (48.29%) patients belonged to age group 30-45 years and 181 (51.71%) patients belonged to age group 46-60 years. Hypomagnesemia was found in 60 (35.50%) patients and 62 (34.25%) patients respectively in age group 30-45 years and age group 46-60 years. Statistically insignificant association of hypomagnesemia with age group was detected with p value 0.8232. Male diabetics were 197 (56.29%) and female diabetics were 153 (43.71%) and hypomagnesemia was noted in 72 (36.55%) male patients and in 50 (32.68%) female patients. Association of hypomagnesemia with gender was statistically insignificant with p value 0.4980

Conclusion: Results of present showed a higher percentage of hypomagnesemia in cases of type-II diabetes mellitus. A higher proportion of male gender was reported as compared to female gender and there is no association of hypomagnesemia with gender. Duration of diabetes, age and obesity were insignificantly associated with hypomagnesemia.

Key words: Diabetes mellitus, endocrine, magnesium, enzyme activator

Corresponding author:**Dr. Adil Abdul Haye,**

Central Park Medical College, Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Adil Abdul Haye et al, A Descriptive Study On Hypomagnesemia In Patients Of Type-II Diabetes Mellitus., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(08).

INTRODUCTION:

The number of people with diabetes is increasing due to population growth, aging, urbanization and increasing prevalence of obesity and physical inactivity.¹ Quantifying the prevalence of diabetes and the number of people affected by diabetes, now and in the future, is important to allow rational planning and allocation of resources.² There are an estimated 23.6 million people in the U.S. (7.8% of the population) with diabetes and 17.9 million being diagnosed, 90% of whom are type 2.³ With prevalence rates doubling between 1990 and 2005, CDC has characterized the increase as an epidemic.⁴ Pakistan is estimated to have 7 million people with diabetes.⁵ Currently it is 8th in the world according to WHO estimation of prevalence of diabetes and by the year 2025 is expected to be 4th with 15 million people with diabetes, representing a 2 fold increase in caseload.⁶ It is also one of the most common chronic diseases affecting children with about 200 children world-wide develop type 1 diabetes every day.⁷

Globally, over 300 million people suffer from type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), and the prevalence is predicted to rise to over 600 million over the next decades.⁸ T2DM is characterized by a combination of insulin deficiency and insulin resistance. The general pathophysiological concept is that hyperglycemia emerges when endogenous insulin secretion can no longer match the increased demand owing to insulin resistance.⁹

Magnesium is the fourth most abundant cation in the human body and the second most abundant intracellular cation.¹⁰ It plays an important role in the carbohydrate metabolism. It serves as a cofactor for all enzymatic reactions that require kinases.¹¹ It is also an essential enzyme activator for neuromuscular excitability and cell permeability, a regulator of ion channels and mitochondrial function, a critical element in cellular proliferation and apoptosis, and an important factor in both cellular and humoral functions.¹²

The disturbance in serum magnesium level i.e. hypomagnesemia has been reported to occur among patients of diabetes mellitus.¹³ The persistent hypomagnesemia leads to raised serum glucose level, insulin resistance and the degree of magnesium depletion correlates positively with serum glucose concentration and the degree of glucosuria.¹⁴

Present study was conducted to evaluate the hypomagnesemia in cases of type-II diabetics. Results of this study may help us to reduce the morbidity related to it by early screening of hypomagnesemia in type-II diabetics.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Department of Medicine, Central Park Medical College Lahore from August 2019 to February 2020. Total 350 type-II diabetics, having age range 30-60 years, either male or female with duration of diabetes ≥ 3 years were selected. Patients with type-I diabetes mellitus, secondary causes of diabetes mellitus (like haemochromatosis, Cushing's disease, acromegaly), chronic diarrhea, hypo-proteinemic states (like chronic liver disease). Patients with acute or chronic diarrheal/ malabsorption states, with thyroid or adrenal dysfunction, history of alcohol intake, history of vitamin or mineral supplements in the recent past, recent metabolic acidosis, pregnancy, lactation, with serum creatinine > 1.5 mg/dl, and on drugs known to affect magnesium levels, were excluded from the study.

Five ml blood sample was drawn from every patient and send to laboratory for Magnesium levels. The normal serum magnesium level considered was 1.8 - 2.5 mg /dl so the value < 1.8 mg /dl was labeled as hypomagnesemia. Findings of the lab test were noted on pre-designed performa along with demographic profile of the patients.

Type 2 diabetes mellitus was diagnosed as per criteria of American diabetic's association:

1. Fasting plasma glucose level higher than 126 mg/dl or
2. Plasma Glucose level exceeding 200 mg/dl at 2 hours in the 75 g oral glucose tolerance test or
3. Symptoms of Diabetes and Random Plasma Glucose > 200 mg/dl or
4. HbA1C $> 6.5\%$.

All the collected data was entered in SPSS version 18 and analyzed. Mean and SD was calculated for numerical data and frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical data.

RESULTS:

Total 350 type-II diabetics were selected and hypomagnesemia was assessed. Mean age of the patients 45.34 ± 8.55 years with age range from 30-60 years and mean duration of diabetes was 6.54 ± 2.43 years. Out of 350 type-II diabetics, hypomagnesemia was found in 122 (35%) patients. (Fig. 1) Selected patients were divided into two age groups i.e. age group 30-45 years and age group 46-60 years. Total 169 (48.29%) patients belonged to age group 30-45 years and 181 (51.71%) patients belonged to age group 46-60 years. Hypomagnesemia was found in 60 (35.50%) patients and 62 (34.25%) patients respectively in age group 30-45 years and age group 46-60 years. Statistically insignificant association of hypomagnesemia with age group was detected with p value 0.8232. (Table 1)

Male diabetics were 197 (56.29%) and female diabetics were 153 (43.71%) and hypomagnesemia was noted in 72 (36.55%) male patients and in 50 (32.68%) female patients. Association of hypomagnesemia with gender was statistically insignificant with p value 0.4980 (Table 2)

Minimum duration of diabetes was 3 years and maximum duration of diabetes was 10 years. Two equal groups was made according to duration of diabetes i.e. 3-7 years group and 8-10 years group. Total 210 (60%) patients belonged to 3-7 years

group and hypomagnesemia was noted in 77 (36.67%) patients. Out of 140 (40%) patients of 8-10 years group, hypomagnesemia was seen in 45 (32.14%) patients. Insignificant association between hypomagnesemia and duration of diabetes mellitus was seen with p value 0.4236. (Table 3) Obese were 140 (40%) and non-obese were 210 (60). Hypomagnesemia was found in 45 (32.14%) patients and 77 (36.67%) patients respectively in obese and non-obese patients. Insignificant association between obesity and hypomagnesemia was seen with p value 0.4236 (Table 4)

Fig. 1: Frequency of hypomagnesemia

Table 1: Association of hypomagnesemia with age

Age Group	Hypomagnesemia		Total	P value
	Yes	No		
30-45	60 (35.50)	109 (64.50)	169 (48.29)	0.8232
46-60	62 (34.25)	119 (65.75)	181 (51.71)	
Total	122 (35)	228 (65)	350	

Table 2: Association of hypomagnesemia with gender

Gender	Hypomagnesemia		Total	P value
	Yes	No		
Male	72 (36.55)	125 (63.45)	197 (56.29)	0.4980
Female	50 (32.68)	103 (67.32)	153 (43.71)	
Total	122 (35)	228 (65)	350	

Table 3: Association of hypomagnesemia with duration of diabetes

Duration of diabetes	Hypomagnesemia		Total	P value
	Yes	No		
3-7	77 (36.67)	133 (63.33)	210 (60)	0.4236
8-10	45 (32.14)	95 (67.86)	140 (40)	
Total	122 (35)	228 (65)	350	

Table 4: Association of hypomagnesemia with obesity

Obesity	Hypomagnesemia		Total	P value
	Yes	No		
Obese	45 (32.14)	95 (67.86)	140 (40)	0.4236
Non-obese	77 (36.67)	133 (63.33)	210 (60)	
Total	122 (35)	228 (65)	350	

DISCUSSION:

Among the endocrine and metabolic disorders associated with magnesium deficiency, diabetes mellitus is the most common.¹⁵ Many studies have shown that mean plasma levels are lower in patients with both type 1 and type 2 diabetes compared with nondiabetic control subjects. Significant negative correlations between magnesium and fasting plasma glucose, HbA1c, HOMA-IR have been shown.¹⁶ The various causes of low magnesium in diabetics include diets low in magnesium, osmotic diuresis causing high renal excretion of magnesium, insensitivity to insulin affecting intracellular magnesium transport and thereby causing increased loss of the extracellular magnesium, rampant use of loop and thiazide diuretics promoting magnesium wasting, diabetic autonomic neuropathies and reduced tubular reabsorption due to insulin resistance.¹⁷

In present study, total 350 type-II diabetics were selected and hypomagnesemia was assessed. Mean age of the patients 45.34 ± 8.55 years with age range from 30-60 years and mean duration of diabetes was 6.54 ± 2.43 years. Out of 350 type-II diabetics, hypomagnesemia was found in 122 (35%) patients. Selected patients were divided into two age groups i.e. age group 30-45 years and age group 46-60 years. Total 169 (48.29%) patients belonged to age group 30-45 years and 181 (51.71%) patients belonged to age group 46-60 years. Hypomagnesemia was found in 60 (35.50%) patients and 62 (34.25%) patients respectively in age group 30-45 years and age group 46-60 years. Statistically insignificant association of hypomagnesemia with age group was detected with p value 0.8232.

In a study by Kauser et al¹⁸ mean age of the diabetics was 55.42 ± 12.65 years which is higher than our study. In same study 62% patients were males and 38% patients were females. In our study, male diabetics were 197 (56.29%) and female diabetics were 153 (43.71%) and hypomagnesemia was noted in 72 (36.55%) male patients and in 50 (32.68%) female patients. Association of hypomagnesemia with gender was statistically insignificant with p value 0.4980. This male to female frequency in similar with our study.

In one study by Siddiqui et al,¹⁹ total 323 diabetics were selected and serum magnesium levels was

studied and found hypomagnesemia in 34.11% patients which is comparable with findings of our study.

Prevalence of low plasma magnesium status in type-II diabetics in several studies, which ranged from 25 to 39%. Prevalence of hypomagnesemia in type-II diabetics in our study was similar to that reported by Nadler et al²⁰ in type-II diabetics, attending outpatient clinics in the US. Walti MK et al²¹ also reported a prevalence of hypomagnesemia in type-II diabetics at 37.6% versus 10.9% in non-diabetic controls in a study conducted in Zurich, Switzerland. The reasons for the high prevalence of magnesium deficiency in diabetes are not clear, but may include increased urinary loss, lower dietary intake, or impaired absorption of magnesium compared to healthy individuals. Hyassat et al²² reported that out of 1105 patients with type 2 diabetes, 210 patients (19%) (95% CI, 16.8%-21.4%) were hypomagnesaemic. Female gender, hypertension, statin therapy, HbA1c between 7-7.9% or $\geq 9\%$ and patients with diabetes duration more than five years were independent risk factors for hypomagnesaemia. No association between hypomagnesaemia and age distribution was found. A cross-sectional study conducted by Seyoum et al²³ included a total of 159 subjects (44 patients with type 1 DM, 69 patients with type 2 DM and 46 non diabetic control) to assess the prevalence of hypomagnesaemia in Ethiopian patients with type-1 and type-2 DM. The study revealed that hypomagnesaemia was present in 65% of patients with diabetes. In other studies, hypomagnesaemia has been shown to occur in 25-38% (6, 17-19) of patients with diabetes, especially in those without good metabolic control.²⁴⁻²⁵ This wide range of difference in the prevalence between our study and other studies might be due to differences in the definition of hypomagnesaemia, techniques of magnesium measurements, and heterogeneity of the selected patient populations. Dasgupta et al,²⁶ hypomagnesemia (Se magnesium < 1.6 mg/dl) was documented in 17 (11.33%) patients with a female:male ratio of 9:8.

CONCLUSION:

Results of present showed a higher percentage of hypomagnesemia in cases of type-II diabetes mellitus. A higher proportion of male gender was reported as compared to female gender and there is no association of hypomagnesemia with gender.

Duration of diabetes, age and obesity were insignificantly associated with hypomagnesemia.

REFERENCES:

1. Thibault V, Bélanger M, LeBlanc E, Babin L, Halpine S, Greene B, Mancuso M. Factors that could explain the increasing prevalence of type 2 diabetes among adults in a Canadian province: a critical review and analysis. *Diabetology & metabolic syndrome*. 2016 Dec;8(1):71.
2. Alqurashi KA, Aljabri KS, Bokhari SA. Prevalence of diabetes mellitus in a Saudi community. *Annals of Saudi medicine*. 2011 Jan;31(1):19.
3. Rother KI. Diabetes treatment—bridging the divide. *The New England journal of medicine*. 2007 Apr 12;356(15):1499.
4. Homer JB, Hirsch GB. System dynamics modeling for public health: background and opportunities. *American journal of public health*. 2006 Mar;96(3):452-8.
5. Wild S, Roglic G, Green A, Sicree R, King H. Global prevalence of diabetes: estimates for the year 2000 and projections for 2030. *Diabetes care*. 2004;27(5):1047–1053.
6. Akhtar S, Khan Z, Rafiq M, Khan A. Prevalence of Type II diabetes in District Dir Lower in Pakistan. *Pakistan journal of medical sciences*. 2016 May;32(3):622.
7. American Diabetes Association. AD (2007). *Diagnosis and Classification of Diabetes Mellitus*. *Diabetes Care*.;30:47.
8. Gommers LM, Hoenderop JG, Bindels RJ, de Baaij JH. Hypomagnesemia in type 2 diabetes: a vicious circle?. *Diabetes*. 2016 Jan 1;65(1):3-13.
9. Hameed I, Masoodi SR, Mir SA, Nabi M, Ghazanfar K, Ganai BA. Type 2 diabetes mellitus: from a metabolic disorder to an inflammatory condition. *World journal of diabetes*. 2015 May 15;6(4):598.
10. Swaminathan R. Magnesium metabolism and its disorders. *The Clinical Biochemist Reviews*. 2003 May;24(2):47.
11. Gröber U, Schmidt J, Kisters K. Magnesium in prevention and therapy. *Nutrients*. 2015 Sep 23;7(9):8199-226.
12. Chhabra S, Chhabra S, Ramessur K, Chhabra N. Hypomagnesemia and its implications in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus- A Review Article . *WebmedCentral Diabetes* 2012;3(12):WMC003878.
13. Gommers LM, Hoenderop JG, Bindels RJ, de Baaij JH. Hypomagnesemia in type 2 diabetes: a vicious circle?. *Diabetes*. 2016 Jan 1;65(1):3-13.
14. Shaikh MK, Devrajani BR, Soomro AA, Ali Shah SZ, Devrajani T, Das T. Hypomagnesemia in Patients with Diabetes mellitus. *World Applied Sciences Journal*. 2011;12(10):1803–6.
15. Hans CP, Sialy R, Bansal DD. Magnesium deficiency and diabetes mellitus. *Current Science*. 2002;1456–1463.
16. El-said N, Sadik N, Mohammed N. Magnesium in type 2 diabetes mellitus and its correlation with glycemic control. *International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*. 2015;1958–63.
17. Schulze MB, Schulz M, Heidemann C, Schienkiewitz A, Hoffmann K, Boeing H. Fiber and magnesium intake and incidence of type 2 diabetes: a prospective study and meta-analysis. *Archives of internal medicine*. 2007 May 14;167(9):956-65.
18. Kausar M, Afreen A, R V, Javarappa D. Study of serum magnesium in type 2 Diabetes Mellitus and its correlation with the modality of treatment- A south Indian study. *International Journal of Medical Science and Public Health*. 2014;3(11):1398.
19. Siddiqui MU, Ali I, Zakariya M, Asghar SP, Ahmed MR, Ibrahim GH. FREQUENCY OF HYPOMAGNESEMIA IN PATIENTS WITH UNCONTROLLED TYPE II DIABETES MELLITUS. *Pakistan Armed Forces Medical Journal*. 2016;66(6).
20. Nadler JC, Rude RK. Disorders of magnesium metabolism. *Endocrinol Metab. Clinic.North.Am*. 1995; 24: 623-41.
21. Walti MK, Zimmermann MB, Hurrell RF. Low plasma magnesium in type-II diabetes. *Swiss Med Wkly*. 2003; 133: 289-92.
22. Hyassat D, AlSitri E, Batieha A, EL-Khateeb M, Ajlouni K. Prevalence of Hypomagnesaemia among Obese Type 2 Diabetic Patients Attending the National Center for Diabetes, Endocrinology and Genetics (NCDEG). *International Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism [Internet]*. 2014 Jul 1 [cited 2018 Oct 21];12(3). Available from: <http://endometabol.com/en/articles/17676.html>
23. Syedmoradi L, Ghasemi A, Zahediasl S, Azizi F. Prevalence of hypo- and hypermagnesemia in an Iranian urban population. *Ann Hum Biol*. 2011;38(2):150–5.
24. Kao WH, Folsom AR, Nieto FJ, Mo JP, Watson RL, Brancati FL. Serum and dietary magnesium and the risk for type 2 diabetes mellitus: the Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities Study. *Arch Intern Med*. 1999;159(18):2151–9.
25. Crook M, Couchman S, Tutt P, Amiel S, Swaminathan R. Erythrocyte, plasma total, ultrafiltrable and platelet magnesium in type 2 (non-insulin dependent) diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes Res*. 1994;27(2):73–9.

26. Dasgupta A, Sarma D, Saikia UK.
Hypomagnesemia in type 2 diabetes mellitus.
Indian J Endocrinol Metab. 2012;16(6):1000–3.